
Development of Remote Services in Banks

Murodova Mohigul Chori kizi

Tashkent State the University of Economics, PhD Associate Professor of the Department of Regional Economics

Abstract: The article identifies urgent problems related to the organizational and economic foundations of the provision of remote banking services by commercial banks and develops scientific proposals aimed at solving them.

Key words: Remote banking services, Inflation, financial boutique, SMS-banking, Internet-banking, Tap-to-phone system, Mobile-banking, Supermarket-banking, financial literacy, IT.

Introduction. Attention is paid to the further increase in the competition in the provision of high-quality remote banking services to the population in the world, to the assessment of the international rating of the efficiency of commercial banks. According to World Bank reports, “40 percent of the first users of digital banking services used online banking services, and in the East Asia and Pacific region - 54 percent, in Latin America and the Caribbean region - 15 percent, and in Europe and Central Asia - 10 percent”[1]. The existence of inconsistencies in the process of providing remote banking services by commercial banks and the varying levels of quality of remote banking services require special attention to be paid to this area.

In the world, attention is being paid to scientific research aimed at developing the provision of remote services by commercial banks and introducing new modern banking services and improving their quality. Scientific research is being conducted on the issues of expanding remote banking services by commercial banks, increasing the culture of providing remote services to customers by banks, increasing the trust of the broad masses of the population in banks, attracting large customers and offering new types of remote services taking into account their demands and suggestions, and providing services with constant consideration of customer opinions.

Literature analysis. As is known, the history of the theory of services provided by banks has gone through several stages. At the initial stage of the development of the theory of banking services, the scientific works of H. Douglas[2] and G. Bryan were devoted to the study of the banking services market and its banking services segment. The second stage, which was devoted to the study of the characteristics of the functioning of the economic systems of countries and the influence of other factors on the banking services market, is reflected in the scientific works of F. Derek[3], O. Donnel, E. Ballarin. At the next, 3rd stage, ideas were put forward on the ideas of the “Financial supermarket” and “financial boutique”. Electronic services provided in the banking services market have become widespread, and cases of mergers and acquisitions of banks have increased. In this regard, the scientific works of D. Gentle, J. Sinki[4], P. Rose can be especially noted.

I.I. Bichkova considers “remote services of commercial banks to be implemented in most cases based on the client’s instructions through computer technologies and the telephone network without visiting the bank”[5]. O.I. Lavrushin defines “remote services of banks are a complex of services of the bank to remotely authorize its clients (individuals and legal entities) to perform various banking operations”[6].

If we pay attention to the opinions of Sh.Z. Abdullaeva[7] about remote banking services, they draw attention to the fact that the development of information technologies is expanding the possibilities of providing financial services on the Internet, advanced firms and commercial banks are now using this opportunity to provide remote services to clients, to carry out electronic money accounts, and that the development of remote management of bank balance sheets in commercial banks of our country is one of the important issues of the day.

We can see that Kh. Khudoyarova[8] emphasized the importance of further developing remote services of commercial banks by proposing "to achieve the strategic goal of improving the retail banking services market, to further improve the retail banking services market and meet the needs of bank customers by introducing modern, innovative "online" services based on standardizing the process of providing retail banking services."

Research results. The increasing number of services provided by commercial banks in our country creates convenience for customers and allows customers to choose a bank based on the quality of banking services. The services provided bring a certain amount of income to commercial banks. An analysis of the activities of commercial banks in Uzbekistan shows that the main place in bank income is occupied by income from various services.

Figure 1. Types of banking services [9].

It has become natural for remote banking services to be performed directly using electronic means. As a result, a new definition of electronic banking has also been used for all remote banking services.

Figure 2. Types of electronic banking[10].

Mobile-Banking is the management of bank cards or accounts through pocket compact computers, communicators and smartphones. It works in an online system. It allows you to work with all types of financial documents. It also creates the opportunity to work in a team, including an encryption mechanism and an electronic signature (EDI).

Phone-Banking is a program for accessing bank accounts and cards by phone. Through this service, you can find out information about current balances, a statement for a certain period by fax, replenish or block cards, pay phone bills, etc.

When using Phone-Banking, the client calls the provided number and, after connecting, switches the phone to voice mode. Following the instructions of the voice menu and selecting the appropriate item, the client can receive the necessary information in the form of a document by voice message or fax.

Video-Banking is a videoconference, that is, an interactive communication system between a bank employee and a client. Usually, a device called a “Kiosk” is used in video banking. This device with a touch screen allows the client to access various information, while also having a live conversation with a bank employee and performing any operation. This device is installed not at home, but in supermarkets, universities and other crowded places. Usually, kiosks are installed in the same place as ATMs (Automatic Teller Machine). This type of service requires some expense and a high-quality Internet connection or network conditions. However, the process of directly seeing each other with a bank employee via video certainly ensures the reliability and error-free operation of this type of service.

Web-Banking is a simplified version of Internet-Banking, does not have an electronic signature (EDI) mechanism, and is designed to provide access to bank cards and accounts via the Internet and any Web browser. This type of banking service is actively used mainly in developed countries such as the USA, Japan and Western Europe. Today, this type of service is used by many people using the standard Internet Explorer program.

WAP-Banking is a service that allows you to access bank cards and accounts via WAP on a mobile device. This allows the client to obtain information about the bank, exchange rates, current balance on the account and cards. In addition, the client can request a statement of his account for the relevant period, top up and block cards, and make WAP payments. The most convenient aspect of this type of service is that it is accessed via the WAP service of any mobile device with Internet access and does not require any special services or programs.

SMS-Banking — a service for accessing bank cards and accounts using SMS. With this type of service, you can receive information about current balances, movements of funds on accounts and cards, and account statements in the form of SMS messages. The client can independently configure the sending of SMS messages via Internet-Banking and PC-Banking. There are also opportunities to subscribe to bank news channels and make SMS requests.

RC-Banking — a service for managing bank cards and accounts in an offline system. It allows you to work with all types of financial documents. It is the result of the evolutionary development of the previously known Bank-Client service. It has an EDS encryption mechanism, provides automatic updating of client components when connected to the bank server, allows for teamwork, and has the ability to interact with accounting programs. In “RC-Banking”, two systems are divided into systems for “large” and “thin” clients.

Recently, banks have been focusing on the format of their retail services, which is designed for “thin clients”, since Internet banking allows customers to work from any computer connected to the Internet without installing special software. “Large clients” are more suitable for working with legal entities.

Along with the users of innovative technologies in the republic, the number of users of remote bank account management systems is also increasing day by day. The bold implementation of information technology achievements in the activities of banks and the creation of excellent programs and the establishment of banking services on their basis have created a solid platform, and today software based on new modern information technologies is being used in practice.

Figure 1. Number of users of the remote banking service system[11].

More than 652 thousand co-branded bank cards were issued by 15 commercial banks, which allow the population to make settlements in the infrastructure of national and foreign payment systems. In order to increase the volume of cashless settlements and stimulate customer purchases, banks, in cooperation with mobile communication operators and payment organizations, launched projects to issue co-branded cards. 380 business entities began using the service, which allows business entities to accept payments through the Tap-to-phone system (without a terminal), introduced as part of the development of contactless payment services.

Conclusion. We have formulated the following conclusions related to the practical situation of providing remote banking services by commercial banks:

1. An analysis of remote banking services provided by commercial banks, their efficiency and quality shows that currently the range of remote services offered by banks to their clients has expanded significantly. Through a single bank mobile application, a client can use banking services without visiting a bank, freely convert funds in national currency into foreign currency without commission, make online deposits and calculate the funds received, receive overdraft loans and repay loans.
2. Through the bank's mobile application, the client will be able to constantly monitor his funds. The creation of such mobile applications creates the basis for saving customers' time and money and attracting more new customers to banks.
3. A modern banking infrastructure based on high technologies is being created in Uzbekistan, providing customers with a wide range of remote services.
4. More and more supermarkets and large shopping centers are being opened in the cities and district centers of Uzbekistan. Banks have the opportunity to increase the efficiency of the services provided using the supermarket banking method, and the implementation of the new Supermarket Banking direction, based on advanced foreign experience, in our opinion, will serve to enrich the range of banking services.

References:

1. World Bank report <https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/press-release/2022/06/29/covid-19-drives-global-surge-in-use-of-digital-payments> based on the data.
2. Douglas H. Bankovskaya politika v oblasti kreditovaniya. - M.: Slovo, 1971. - 508 p.
3. Derek F. Global strategic banking. - M.: Economics and finance, 1990. - 385 c.
4. Sinky Dj. Financial management and commercial banking and industry financial management. Per. English - Moscow: Alpina Business Books, 2007. - 1018 p.
5. Bychkova I.I. Technological innovations in the sale of banking products / I. I. Bichkova, O. G. Semenyuta // Modern management technologies. - 2016. - No. 3 (63). - P. 55-62.

6. Lavrushin O.I. Money, credit, banks: Textbook / Ed. Honored. deyat. nauki RF, Dr. econ. nauki, prof. O.I.Lavrushina. -M.: KNORUS, 2016.- 576 p.
7. Abdullaeva Sh.Z.. Banking. T.: "ECONOMICS-FINANCE" 2017. pp. 535-536.
8. Khudayarova X.A. Improving the practice of retail banking services in Uzbekistan. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics. T.: 2020. 63 p.
9. Khudayarova X.A. Improving the practice of retail banking services in Uzbekistan. Abstract of the dissertation for the degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics. T.: 2020. 63 p
10. cbu.uz.- Official website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan
11. cbu.uz.- Official website of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan website